

REPORT FIRST EL-CSID ANNUAL DISSEMINATION EVENT

Brussels, 12 May 2016

About the EL-CSID Project

The EU funded project “European Leadership in Cultural, Science and Innovation Diplomacy” (EL-CSID) analyses the relevance of cultural, science and innovation diplomacy for EU external relations, locating developments in these fields in the evolving global context.

The ambition of EL-CSID is to make explicit the assumptions underpinning much of the practices at work in the EU’s cultural, science and innovation diplomacy work. Its overall goal is to contribute to a strengthening of EU policy towards the use of science, culture and innovation in its wider diplomacy as well as to deepening scholarly understanding of diplomacy as an abiding institution.

The project is convened by a consortium of nine partners from Belgium, Germany, Kazakhstan, Singapore, Slovenia, Turkey and the United Kingdom, and is coordinated at the Institute of European Studies (IES) at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel, with Prof. Dr. Luk Van Langenhove as the Scientific Coordinator.

The project runs from March 2016 to February 2019. It has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 693799. Further details about the project can be found at: www.el-csid.eu.

Context of the Dissemination Event

The first EL-CSID dissemination event was organised to officially launch the project to the public. It aimed at presenting the EL-CSID research agenda to both the academic and policy communities as well as at gaining insights into the stakeholders’ views and expectations. This early discussion helped the EL-CSID consortium further refine its perspectives on its core concepts of cultural, science and diplomacy and ensure its academic and policy agenda are integrated.

To these ends, the **first session** of the event was a roundtable discussion that provided for interaction among the EL-CSID researchers and a small group of EU officials and policy-makers. The **second session** was an academic panel that provided a platform for the EL-CSID researchers to discuss the early steps of their research on cultural and science diplomacy with a large academic audience. It was held in the context of the European Union in International Affairs (EUIA) Conference.

The EUIA is a joint venture in which two of the EL-CSID partner institutions—the IES and UNU-CRIS—are involved. For further details about the conference, please consult the [conference website](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693799.

Roundtable Agenda and Participants

Chair: **Luk Van Langenhove**, EL-CSID Scientific Coordinator, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

The roundtable discussion addressed the following four topics:

- To what extent can cultural and science diplomacy enhance the interests of the EU in the current context?
- What would contribute to maximising the impact of the EU’s cultural and science diplomacy?
- What key issues should the research agenda on the EU’s cultural, science and innovation diplomacy address?
- What are the current Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) of the EU’s cultural and science diplomacy?

The session was held under Chatham House Rule, meaning that “participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.”¹

Roundtable participants:

Hughes Becquart, DG Education and Culture

Maria da Graça Carvalho, DG Research and Innovation

Pietro De Matteis, Service for Foreign Policy Instruments

Aline Humbert, DG Research and Innovation

Sana Outchati, Cultural Diplomacy Platform

Liliana Pasecinic, Joint Research Centre

Vincent Reillon, European Parliamentary Research Service

Jonathan Van Meerbeek, DG International Development and Cooperation

Walter Zampieri, DG Education and Culture

EL-CSID Researchers:

Ana Amaya, United Nations University

Caterina Carta, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Richard Higgott, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Jos Leijten, Joint Institute for Innovation Policy

Ulrich Schreiterer, Wissenschaftszentrum Berlin für Sozialforschung

Diane Stone, University of Warwick and University of Canberra

Selin Senocak, Centre d’Etudes Diplomatiques et Stratégiques

Georgios Terzis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Rapporteurs:

Léonie Maes, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Eva Seiwert, United Nations University

¹ Chatham House website: <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about/chatham-house-rule>

The roundtable participants welcomed this highly topical discussion. They acknowledged the important and growing role the EU is playing in culture and science and the numerous collaborations it has established worldwide in these domains. The participants also highlighted the potential that the EU has at its disposal to project its influence and thinking in the international arena. They, also acknowledged that there were some constraints and underscored the absence of and the **need for an overall EU Strategy for Cultural and Science Diplomacy (CSD)**.

The need for a strategic approach to Cultural and Science Diplomacy is already acknowledged at the EU level. Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation Carlos Moedas is devoting considerable attention to Science Diplomacy, which he believes can “play a leading role in our global outreach for its uniting power”², and is keen on developing a structured SD strategy. Similarly, High-Representative Federica Mogherini is preparing a Cultural Diplomacy Strategy to be presented to the European Parliament and Council at the end of May 2016.³

What would be the key elements of an overall CSD strategy?

- **Member State-driven:**
 - MS have a **natural legitimacy** for conducting CSD activities.
 - MS have significant **Foreign Service and scientific capacities**.
 - Some MS already have a developed **agenda** or guidelines for C/SD (e.g. Switzerland, Spain, etc.).
 - The meeting noted a range of successful instances of CSD.

- **Concerted and coordinated:**
 - MS to agree on a **joint approach** that taps into the existing potential by bringing together the capacities and resources of all.
 - Creation of a **space for CSD at the EU level**.

- **Value-related:**
 - The EU aspires to develop a strategic and structured approach to CSD as a natural **extension of the European values**.
 - The community of researchers advised **caution** when connecting CSD to European values in order to avoid misunderstandings. The language used to pitch CSD is extremely important.
 - There is a need to distinguish between cultural dialogue and cultural diplomacy as well as values and norms. The following text, extracted from the paper from Higgott and Van Langenhove, throws some light on this necessary distinction:

“Culture, norms and values are not the same thing. Culture, from its German origins meaning ‘self-realization’, reflects a society’s historically determined, moral, religious and national beliefs. Norms influence the prescriptive practices of actors. They are culturally determined. One culture does not set the course of action for another. Cultural dialogues are usually about norms as practice, not values, and they

² Carlos Moedas, “The EU approach to science diplomacy”, European Institute, Washington (June 1, 2015). Speech available at: [European Commission website](#)

³ European Union External Action, “Culture at the very heart of Europe’s external action”, EEAS (April 20, 2016). Available at: [EEAS website](#)

are adaptive. It is the evolving nature of norms that makes cultural diplomacy a difficult and at times unpredictable instrument in the pursuit of a state's foreign policy."⁴

- Besides values, attention devoted to **science and technology ethics**; a global ethics group is newly appointed at the EU level.
- **Outward-looking:**
 - Significant **interest from partner and third countries** to engage with the EU in the domains of culture and science. CSD can indirectly help widen EU influence globally.
 - Strategy should be **developed in conjunction with EU partners** since they are the ultimate beneficiaries of this strategy.
 - Contributions might not be equal in material terms, but the language and practice of cooperation on **equal terms** is crucial.
 - **Open space** for cultural and science cooperation that reflects European principles. This way, the EU fosters better collaboration by opening windows in a structural way, by setting the scene as a mean for framing the discussion.

What are the challenges to its formulation and implementation?

- **Conceualisation:** not all that qualifies as CSD is labelled as such, and scientists might not be aware that they act as diplomatic agents
- **Involvement:** of EU national ministries in the debate on EU CSD is key
- **Willingness:** of EU MS to pool their Cultural, Scientific and Foreign Service resources
- **Foreign Policy objectives:** CSD strategy closely linked to FP priorities and in line with the Global Strategy on Foreign and Security Policy for the EU to be issued in June 2016
- **European values:** the extent to which and how they are reflected in an EU CSD strategy must be precisely calibrated.
- **Funding and resources:** only 4% of the framework programme funding allocated to CSD, only 10 EU scientific *attachés*.
- **Leadership:** there is no concrete distribution of CSD competencies between the EU and its MS, and a strong leadership will be needed for the formulation and implementation of a Commission CSD strategy.

⁴ Richard Higgott and Luk Van Langenhove, "Cultural and Science Diplomacy in the early 21st century: Can we talk of a 'Practice Turn' in European Policy?", *paper presented at the EUIA conference, Brussels* (May 12, 2016).

What are the current Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) of the EU in the domain of cultural and science diplomacy?

<p style="text-align: center;">Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tradition of scientific excellence and collaborative programmes • Scientific capacities of MS-level research institutions • Culture as major element of cooperation with rest of the world • Social value of science (societal studies) • Positive perceptions of EU culture and science abroad 	<p style="text-align: center;">Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of coordination of MS capacities • Questions concerning EU legitimacy • Mismatch between EU ambition and resources/funding available • Lack of information-sharing, even among EU institutions • Inability to define specific competencies of EU and MS • Lack of coordinated leadership
<p style="text-align: center;">Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current enthusiasm for and development of scientific collaborations all over the world • Growing external expectations of collaboration in cultural domain • Potential to link research to FP • Dialogue on Culture and Science as opening to other discussions • Core role of science and SD in the global sustainability agenda 	<p style="text-align: center;">Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New nationalism • Potentially possessive inward-looking attitude of MS Foreign Services • Risk of fragmented policy approach because of the many actors involved

At the end of the discussion, the participants expressed their strong interest in pursuing this debate further and the need to enhance interaction between the research and policy-making communities.

Academic Panel on “European Cultural and Science Diplomacy: An Agenda for Research”

Panel Agenda and Paper Presenters

Chairs: **Luk Van Langenhove and Richard Higgott**, Vrije Universiteit Brussel
Discussant: **Caterina Carta**, Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Paper presentations:

- The Practice Turn: Towards a new theory of cultural and science diplomacy in the early 21st century, **Richard Higgott and Luk Van Langenhove**
- Networking science diplomacy in transnational governance, **Diane Stone**
- Leveraging science for European foreign policy: Bare necessities, global challenges and soft power, **Ulrich Schreiterer**
- Media potential in cultural and science diplomacy, **Georgios Terzis**
- The European Neighbourhood Policy: A ‘paradigm shift’ for the European cultural diplomacy, **Selin Senocak**

The panel session was attended by approximately 40 conference participants. The papers presented are work in progress and will be published on the [EL-CSID website](#) at a later stage of the project.

Stay Informed about the EL-CSID activities and publications!

There are many ways to be kept informed of the work conducted by the EL-CSID consortium and to interact with us!

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